

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities

DELIVERABLE 4.1

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN
EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY
COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable identifier	D4.1
Deliverable title	Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities
Grant Agreement number	: 101079608
Project acronym	: OPERAS-PLUS
Project title	: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure
Funding Scheme	: HORIZON-INFRADEV-2021-DEV-02
Project's coordinator Organisation	: Max Weber Stiftung – MWS
E-mail address	: kaiser@maxweberstiftung.de
Website	: https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/
WP and tasks contributing	: WP4 (all tasks)
WP leader	: IBL PAN

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Dissemination level	: Public (PU)
Due date	: 2024/11/30
Delivery date	: 2024/11/26
Authors	: Magdalena Wnuk, Maciej Maryl, Françoise Gouzi, Tomasz Umerle
Contributors	: Sy Holsinger, Ronald Snijder, Elena Sokolova, Graham Stone
Reviewers	: Jadranka Stojanovski, Fotis Mystakopoulos
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	: 10.5281/zenodo.14221728

Executive summary

The OPERAS Innovation Lab is a collaborative initiative dedicated to supporting and advancing innovative services and solutions for scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH), paving development pathways for OPERAS Research Infrastructure. Innovation is discussed here in the context of scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities. It is defined as **novel approaches, tools, or workflows that enhance the creation, dissemination, and evaluation of scholarship**. This approach underscores the Lab's dual focus as both an **observatory**, monitoring researchers' evolving needs, and an **accelerator**, providing direct support for the development and implementation of innovative solutions.

The report is based on the analysis of the case studies illustrating various aspects of innovation in scholarly communication, such as two journals embracing new online publishing methods, a toolkit for knowledge sharing, and a metadata-driven book recommender. The report proposes guidelines pertinent to support for such outputs: **Sustainability** (transcending the constraints of funding cycles, **Networking and visibility** (reaching the audience and collaborators), **Research assessment** (recognition of the innovative outputs).

Building upon these insights and international declarations and initiatives, Lab proposes ten specific criteria for assessing innovative outputs: **Novelty** (originality of idea), **Utility** (addressing needs), **User Engagement** (usability and collaboration), **User Responsiveness** (accessibility and adaptability), **Impact and Collaboration** (societal interaction and knowledge exchange), **Bridging Potential** (multi- and interdisciplinary approaches), **Support and Training** (documentation and user assistance), **Sustainability** (long-term maintenance and resources), **Peer Review** (open and transparent evaluation), and **Reusability/Reproducibility** (openness and data sharing).

The case-study analysis revealed varying levels of compliance with the criteria, highlighting the need for tailored support for innovators. This work aligns with the broader research assessment reform movement, advocating for a more inclusive evaluation of scholarly outputs, to which the Lab aims to contribute.

The Lab is moving forward with a dual focus: **observing trends and accelerating the implementation of innovative solutions**. Through research, collaboration, and community engagement, the Lab aims to foster a thriving ecosystem for innovation in open scholarly communication, solidifying OPERAS's position as a leader in the field.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AHSS	Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences
C ² DH	The Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
CARE	CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DH	Digital Humanities
Diamond OA	Diamond Open Access model

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable. Accessible. Interoperable. Reusable.
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
IBL PAN	The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences
IDR/TRD	inter- and trans-disciplinary
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PID	Persistent Unique Identifier
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RI	Research Infrastructures
RPO	Research Performing Organizations
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TARA	Tools to Advance Research Assessment

WP	Work Package
----	--------------

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Introduction

The OPERAS Innovation Lab is a collaborative initiative dedicated to supporting and advancing innovative services and solutions for scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH), paving development pathways for the development of OPERAS Research Infrastructure. This deliverable reports on the Lab's ongoing work within Work Package 4 (WP4) of the OPERAS-Plus project, which focuses on strengthening the Lab's capacity. The OPERAS Innovation Lab aims to establish itself as part of the OPERAS service catalogue, providing guidance and support to stakeholders who wish to engage with innovative scholarly outputs and facilitating connections with relevant e-infrastructure providers. This report, therefore, serves as a key instrument in achieving the Lab's objectives to:

- **Structure and integrate.** Define the OPERAS Innovation Lab's position within OPERAS' network by fostering collaborative relationships with OPERAS members and other e-infrastructure providers who offer services for innovative and FAIR outputs.
- **Inform and educate.** Provide the OPERAS community with coherent and up-to-date knowledge and guidelines on innovations in scholarly communication.
- **Evaluate and prototype.** Prototyping new services, outputs, and evaluation approaches enhances the prestige and recognition of innovative outputs.
- **Support and promote.** Offer practical support for developing and sustaining innovative scholarly communication services in SSH.

These objectives, pursued through the activities detailed in this report, represent the Lab's commitment to driving positive change within the landscape of scholarly communication. Thus, the work presented here encompasses the guidelines for the community and the means to implement lasting support for innovative scholarly communication within OPERAS and beyond.

Becoming the OPERAS Innovation Lab

The OPERAS Innovation Lab already has a rich history rooted in collaborative research and community engagement. Its foundations were laid by the comprehensive research

within Work Package 6 (Innovation in and for OPERAS) of the OPERAS-P project¹, a comprehensive initiative that sought to map the landscape of scholarly communication and identify critical challenges and opportunities for its future development. This study, which involved extensive consultation with over a thousand stakeholders across 33 countries, culminated in a robust report on the future of scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities², outlining recommendations for systemic change.

The OPERAS-P report not only provided a detailed analysis of the current state of scholarly communication but also highlighted the crucial role OPERAS could play in driving innovation and fostering collaboration within the field. It emphasised the need for new services, tools, training, and advocacy efforts to address the evolving needs of researchers, publishers, and other stakeholders. This laid the groundwork for establishing the OPERAS Innovation Lab, an initiative IBL PAN (The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences) spearheaded to translate these recommendations into action within the current project, OPERAS-PLUS.

Building on the momentum generated by OPERAS-P, the Lab was tasked with conducting further research into user needs and prototyping innovative services. By engaging directly with researchers and other stakeholders, the Lab sought to identify practical challenges and develop solutions to facilitate knowledge sharing and enhance the dissemination of research outputs. This user-centric approach ensured that the Lab's activities remained closely aligned with the actual needs of the community it served. The Lab is also deeply committed to the principles outlined in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) agreement, advocating for a shift towards a more qualitative and responsible evaluation of research and broadening the scope of the broadly recognised scholarly outputs. In line with this commitment, the Lab actively prototypes the evaluation of novel research outputs, providing guidance and concrete solutions for the community to navigate the evolving landscape of research assessment.

The OPERAS Innovation Lab underwent a structural evolution, transitioning into a two-part structure comprising an Observatory and an Accelerator. The Observatory focuses on monitoring trends and gathering insights into the evolving landscape of scholarly communication, ensuring that the Lab remains at the forefront of

¹ <https://operas.hypotheses.org/operas-p>

² Avanço et al. „Future of Scholarly Communication. Forging an Inclusive and Innovative Research Infrastructure for Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences and Humanities”. Zenodo, 2021. 10.5281/zenodo.5017705

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

developments in the field. The Accelerator, on the other hand, is dedicated to fostering the development and implementation of new solutions, providing support and resources to researchers and other stakeholders exploring innovative approaches to scholarly communication. This transformation reflects the Lab's ongoing commitment to both understanding and shaping the future of scholarly communication.

As the OPERAS Innovation Lab evolves, its future focus will be scaling innovation through strategic piloting and partnership expansion, embedding sustainable processes into the OPERAS infrastructure. This includes developing funding mechanisms for piloting innovative services, serving as a bridge enabling the collaboration between the industry and academic partners, and driving the adoption of new models for open scholarly communication. OPERAS Innovation Lab is dedicated to establishing a lasting centre for advancing scholarly communication, ensuring OPERAS remains a leader in shaping the future of scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities.

Chapters overview

Chapter 1: What is Innovation? This chapter establishes a pragmatic understanding of innovation within the context of scholarly communication, exploring diverse perspectives and approaches, particularly those reflected in the Lab's dual focus as both an observatory and an accelerator.

Chapter 2: Showcasing Innovation Through Case Studies. This section examines a range of case studies demonstrating exemplary, innovative work in scholarly communication. These include two journals, the *Journal for Digital History*³ and *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*⁴, illustrating diverse approaches to online publishing and the dissemination of non-traditional outputs; the SHAPE-ID toolkit⁵, which facilitates knowledge sharing and reuse through novel publication methods; and a book recommender system that leverages software and open metadata to support reading choices. Through these examples, the chapter highlights the challenges and opportunities associated with innovative scholarly communication, focusing on the practical needs and solutions relevant to SSH researchers.

Chapter 3: Evaluation and Research Assessment. Addressing the critical issue of the perceived prestige of innovative outputs, this chapter explores the limitations of current

³ <https://journalofdigitalhistory.org/en>

⁴ <https://transformations.episciences.org/>

⁵ <https://www.shapeidtoolkit.eu/>

evaluation mechanisms that often prioritise traditional forms of publishing. It argues for recognising and properly assessing a more comprehensive range of scholarly projects and outputs, focusing on the mentioned case studies and applying a new set of qualitative criteria. Building this new evaluation framework will help reviewers in their peer review activities and better recognise innovative projects crucial to SSH communities. However, they often remain invisible in formal peer review and research evaluation processes.

Chapter 4: Structure and Future of the Lab. This concluding chapter outlines the OPERAS Innovation Lab's vision for the future, detailing its structure and strategic objectives. It presents a blueprint for establishing the Lab as the central knowledge hub for the OPERAS community, offering guidance and support to stakeholders engaged with innovative outputs and fostering connections with relevant e-infrastructure providers.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

1. What is innovation?

OPERAS Innovation Lab aims to study and accelerate innovation in scholarly communication. In doing so, it explores the variety of novel tools, projects, and approaches in the social sciences and humanities. According to the classical economic definition by Joseph Schumpeter, innovation is a practical implementation of ideas that introduce research and accelerate innovation in scholarly communication, new products, services, processes, or even a new organisational structure⁶. In other words, it is something new put into practice⁷. In Schumpeter's approach, however, innovation isn't just about adding something new to existing structures but transforming and disrupting them to create new value. Though designed for market studies, this understanding of innovation could be successfully applied to other fields, such as scholarly ecosystems. Within academia, this concept highlights the role of groundbreaking research, new methodologies, digital transformation and novel ideas in advancing scholarly communication.

Open Science, an approach to scholarly communication that has gained momentum in the last couple of decades, has transformed the understanding of how science should be produced and communicated, mainly through practices like Open Access. Open Science flourished in parallel with the digitisation of scientific research, providing a wide range of opportunities for researchers, publishers, science managers and infrastructure providers, resulting in innovative ways of producing and disseminating knowledge⁸. Poole referred to digital humanities and innovation as a "greatly unexplored area"⁹. OPERAS Lab agrees with this diagnosis and established an

⁶ Schumpeter, Joseph A. 1934. *The Theory of Economic Development: An Inquiry into Profits, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle*. Harvard Economic Studies. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

⁷ Gulbrandsen, Magnus, and Siri Aanstad. 2014. 'Is Innovation a Useful Concept for Arts and Humanities Research?' *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education* 14 (January):10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022214533890>.

⁸ Beck, Susanne, Carsten Bergenholtz, Marcel Bogers, Tiare-Maria Brasseur, Marie Louise Conradsen, Diletta Di Marco, Andreas P. Distel, et al. 2022. 'The Open Innovation in Science Research Field: A Collaborative Conceptualisation Approach'. *Industry and Innovation* 29 (2): 136–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2020.1792274>; Gulbrandsen, Magnus, and Siri Aanstad. 2014. 'Is Innovation a Useful Concept for Arts and Humanities Research?' *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education* 14 (January):9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022214533890>; Rieger, Oya Y. 2008. 'Opening Up Institutional Repositories: Social Construction of Innovation in Scholarly Communication'. *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 11 (3). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0011.301>.

⁹ Poole, Alex H. 2017. "'A Greatly Unexplored Area": Digital Curation and Innovation in Digital Humanities'. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 68 (7): 1772–81. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23743>

Observatory to chart the landscape of innovative projects and approaches in the SSH fields, focusing on digitisation, digitalisation, and open practices.

Interviews conducted during the OPERAS-P project provided insights into how scholars perceive and engage with innovation in scholarly communication¹⁰ (Maryl et al., 2021). Researchers largely viewed innovation as a means to enhance the dissemination and impact of their work, mainly through expanded reach and engagement with diverse audiences. Innovation was understood as technological advancements, enabling the creation of novel formats like computational essays, web books, and video essays, which allow for more affluent and interactive knowledge sharing. Innovation was also associated with increased accessibility, encompassing initiatives to make more traditional outputs, such as articles, monographs and grey literature, more readily available through digital platforms.

However, despite recognising the potential of innovative scholarly communication, researchers also identified significant barriers to its adoption. Concerns surrounding discoverability, perceived prestige, and recognition within current evaluation systems often led scholars to prioritise traditional publication venues. This was particularly true for early career researchers who felt more constrained by the prevailing academic reward structures. Furthermore, the lack of digital competencies and the perceived complexity of specific tools and platforms presented obstacles for some researchers. The findings underscored the need for support structures, including training, workshops, and user-friendly services, to empower researchers to embrace innovative approaches and ensure that these approaches are appropriately recognised and valued within the academic ecosystem.

This emphasis on competencies, recognition, and technical support has become a central focus of the OPERAS Innovation Lab's current work and the basis of its dual approach to innovation, which can be defined as **novel approaches, tools, or workflows that enhance the creation, dissemination, and evaluation of scholarship within the social sciences and humanities**. This dual perspective is also applied to the assessment of 1) **innovative projects** (service, tool, platform, infrastructure) and 2) **innovative research outputs** (datasets, software, protocols, multimedia materials, video recording, ephemeral or experimental scholarly outputs, training materials, etc.). Hence, **the primary focus of these guidelines is on evaluating the innovative project**

¹⁰ Maryl, Maciej, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Agnieszka Szulińska, Anna Buchner, Piotr Wciślik, Iva Melinščak Zlodi, Jadranka Stojanovski, et al. 2021. 'OPERAS-P Deliverable D6.5: Report on the Future of Scholarly Writing in SSH', April. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922512>.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

as a whole – encompassing the project, service, or tool itself – rather than solely on the content it produces. While there are instances where the project and its content are intertwined, the emphasis here is on assessing the project's overall innovation. For example, a new publishing platform that enables scholars to publish innovative research in digital humanities would be evaluated as an innovative project, not just for the innovative research it publishes.

The dual approach to innovation within the Lab is reflected in its structure as both an observatory and an accelerator. On the one hand, the observatory adopts a user-centric perspective, closely monitoring the evolving needs of individual researchers concerning innovative outputs, digital competencies, and reward structures. It acts as a sentinel, identifying and supporting emerging trends in scholarly communication to ensure the Lab's activities remain aligned with the community's needs. In essence, the observatory provides a critical understanding of "innovation" as it is understood and experienced by researchers. It informs the Lab's strategic direction and enables it to effectively address the challenges and opportunities of pursuing a more open and inclusive scholarly communication system.

On the other hand, the accelerator focuses on providing direct support to specific initiatives and services deemed strategically meaningful for OPERAS. It actively fosters the development and implementation of innovative solutions and services. The accelerator will utilise a variety of methods to provide support for innovators in the field of SSH. A scholarly ecosystem requires specific approaches since it does not focus on profits but on the social benefits resulting from knowledge production. Despite being different from business values and objectives steering academic production, some methodologies and tools for accelerating innovation developed for entrepreneurship, such as co-design or agile management, apply to academia¹¹.

This dual approach allows the OPERAS Innovation Lab to effectively bridge the gap between individual needs and systemic transformation, driving progress towards a more open, inclusive, and dynamic scholarly communication landscape.

¹¹ Yordanova, Zornitsa, Nikolay Stoimenov, Olga Boyanova, and Ivan Ivanchev. 2019. 'The Long Way from Science to Innovation – A Research Approach for Creating an Innovation Project Methodology'. In *Business Information Systems*, edited by Witold Abramowicz and Rafael Corchuelo, 371–80. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20485-3_29.

2. Showcasing Innovation Through Case Studies

This report presents three diverse case studies, each exploring a different facet of innovative scholarly communication in SSH¹².

Sustaining an online journal: The case of the Journal for Digital History provides insights into the challenges and opportunities of maintaining a born-digital academic journal. This case study examines the journal's operational model, community engagement strategies, and approaches to long-term sustainability. The Transformations: A DARIAH Journal, developed by one of OPERAS' partners (DARIAH-EU), offers a platform for publishing non-traditional research outputs. This case study analyses the journal's innovative approach to publication formats, peer review processes, and its role in disseminating project results beyond traditional articles.

Prototyping software services for open science: This case study investigates the development of a recommender system for open access books based on text and data mining. It explores the technical aspects of building such a system, its potential to enhance the discoverability of open-access resources, and general considerations surrounding the use of text and data mining in an academic context.

Novel publication of project outputs: The SHAPE-ID toolkit, developed to support the publication of hands-on knowledge and resources on evaluating interdisciplinary work in arts, humanities and social sciences (AHSS), exemplifies innovative approaches to scholarly communication. This case study analyses the toolkit's functionalities, its potential to facilitate knowledge sharing and reuse, and its impact on researchers' workflows and dissemination practices.

2.1. Methodology

2.1.1. Assumptions

The data collection and analysis of the cases was conducted according to three key research questions:

¹² The focus of OPERAS Innovation Lab is on the field of social sciences and humanities. However, innovation, and the innovative case studies selected for the Work Package 4, tend to have a broader scope and contribute to the arts as well. Therefore, in the report we refer to SSH and AHSS depending on the particular context we address.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Definition. What is the goal of the project?

- a. clarification of the project's scope: goals, users, technologies, accessibility, funding,
- b. interviewing the authors and contributors on the project's scope,
- c. analysis of bibliometrics and usage data.

Evaluation. How is the project innovative?

- a. shortages and limitations,
- b. revision of the goals and value proposition,
- c. designing sustainability models for the project.

Research Assessment. What is the scholarly value of the project?

All research questions were addressed with the mixed-method approach employing three diverse methods: desk research, group interviews, and a validation workshop. The case studies will be thoroughly presented in section 2.1.3.

2.1.2. Selection of cases

The case studies were selected for several key reasons:

Diversity of challenges and approaches. The selected cases represent a range of innovative approaches to scholarly communication, encompassing technological development, community building, and alternative publication models. This diversity allows for a comprehensive exploration of the challenges and opportunities facing researchers who adopt innovative dissemination strategies.

Preliminary work. The OPERAS Innovation Lab had established contact with selected initiatives prior to the project submission, recognising their potential for showcasing advanced innovative practices and addressing real-world challenges in scholarly communication.

Addressing actual needs. By focusing on the experiences of researchers, open science officers, and other practitioners actively engaged in these initiatives, the case study addresses the practical needs and concerns of those exploring innovative forms of scholarly communication within SSH.

It is important to note that the original selection of case studies included *Projet Savoirs*. However, due to the discontinuation of this project, it was replaced with Transformations: A DARIAH Journal, which had been set up at that time by one of the OPERAS-Plus partners (DARIAH-EU) and allowed for an immediate application of solutions developed within the Lab. This substitution ensured the continued relevance of the research while aligning with the Lab's focus on supporting the development and implementation of innovative tools and services.

2.1.3. Research design

The whole research process took six months. Firstly, a desk study was conducted mainly for the definition phase (November 2023 -January 2024). Secondly, four in-depth group interviews with the creators of selected projects were conducted online (January-February 2024). Thirdly, findings were summarised and demonstrated to the participants of the validation workshop at the OPERAS Conference on 24 April 2024 in Zadar (March-April 2024).¹³

Desk research

The desk research criteria were developed based on the previous work on the Lab published in OPERAS-P deliverables¹⁴. The categories for the desk research, with detailed descriptions, were added in Annex 1.

Interviews

After the collection of information on each of the cases, four interviews with the creators of the projects were arranged and conducted in February 2024:

Interviewee	Date
Recommender system for OAPEN	01.02.2024
Transformations: A DARIAH Journal	05.02.2024

¹³

<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/conference-workshops-details/#workshop-2>

¹⁴

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Journal of Digital History	20.02.2024
SHAPE-ID Toolkit	22.02.2024

The interviews, lasting ca. 60 minutes each, aimed at broadening the knowledge about the project's scope and future developments. The creators were asked to name the main challenges and define the project's value proposition that makes it unique and useful. The interviews were conducted and analysed according to factors relating to value proposition, target audiences, implementation, and challenges (please see the interview scenario in Annex 2). Cases will be presented according to the questionnaire in section 3.2.

Validation Workshop

A validation workshop was employed to evaluate the preliminary results and to discuss the case studies within the community of potential users at the OPERAS 2024 Conference in Zadar¹⁵. The workshop provided a platform to validate the Lab's case study findings and co-create actionable guidelines with experts and practitioners in open scholarly communication. The results were used to formulate further guidelines for projects similar to those selected for the case study (see section 2.3).

2.1. Case studies' description and evaluation

This section summarises findings on four innovative projects selected to be a part of the OPERAS Innovation Lab case study. The analysis of each case is structured according to four categories: value proposition, target audience, implementation and challenges. Each section concludes with OPERAS Innovation Lab guidelines for creators on addressing the challenges and solving the main problems. Additionally to this analysis, each project and the results of the case study were presented on the Observatory blog.¹⁶

¹⁵ The workshop subpage at the OPERAS conference in Zadar: <https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/conference-workshops-details/#workshop-2>

¹⁶ <https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/innovative-outputs/innovation-lab-case-study/>

2.2.1. SHAPE-ID Toolkit

The SHAPE-ID toolkit¹⁷ was developed within the [SHAPE-ID](https://www.shapeid.eu/)¹⁸ (Shaping Interdisciplinary Practices in Europe) project, a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (822705). The toolkit is a collection of resources regarding inter- and trans-disciplinary (IDR/TRD) collaboration within AHSS. The material is organised around goals users might want to achieve, such as understanding IDR/TDR, funding collaborative research, evaluating IDR/TDR or developing IDR/TDR research skills. Some resources come from specific disciplines or organisations but were selected because they have valuable messages for a more general audience. Users can browse the resources using filters by category of resources. The creators also prepared "guided pathways", making it easier to search through the database for specific users, such as researchers or science managers.

Value proposition

The toolkit serves as a central hub for knowledge on interdisciplinary methodologies and research, consolidating diverse information and resources into a single, accessible platform. A team member explained that they aimed to gather and organise this disparate information, making it easier for people to discover and understand its potential applications. While the primary focus is on the AHSS, the toolkit's interdisciplinary nature also extends its relevance to other fields.

The toolkit helps navigate knowledge available from various sources. It collects and organises resources to provide pathways for multiple stakeholders to understand what's needed on different levels of inter- and transdisciplinarity in AHSS. As the project team told us during the interview: "When we were building it, we were very much aware that there was a lot of, as somebody has just said, there was a lot of material out there already. So what we wanted to create was a portal to guide people, largely to guide people towards existing material." This approach resulted in creating the guided pathways, which allow exploration of the resources from two entry points: the user's role and the research's objective (goals).

Target audiences

SHAPE-ID toolkit is aimed at all levels of experience, especially newcomers. According to the website description, it is designed to serve as a knowledge gateway for:

¹⁷ <https://www.shapeidtoolkit.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.shapeid.eu/>

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

- Researchers from any discipline, particularly AHSS, who want to learn more about IDR/TDR and do collaborative research and IDR/TDR careers.
- Funders and policymakers interested in understanding why IDR/TDR is worth investing in and how to develop and evaluate IDR/TDR funding programmes.
- Staff in research-performing organisations with roles in educating, training, supporting, hiring, evaluating and promoting researchers.
- Societal partners who wish to engage in knowledge co-creation with researchers, e.g. partners from industry, civil society organisations, the cultural sector and citizens¹⁹.

Implementation

SHAPE-ID Toolkit was implemented as an outcome of a larger project in an international consortium led by Trinity College in Dublin. The tool was developed by an external service provider in six months and is hosted in the Trinity College infrastructure. In the interview, the team described the implementation process as smooth and successful. They recounted starting with a general concept for the toolkit, followed by a design meeting in late 2020 to define core features and inform the request for tenders. While acknowledging that projects rarely adhere perfectly to schedules, they outlined the key milestones: agreeing on the aesthetic and user experience design by the end of January, receiving a draft version for review in mid-February, and conducting internal user testing.

Challenges

After completing the project, the main challenge was its sustainability. The creators of the toolkit did not manage to secure funding for the website, and the team leader from Trinity College had to resign from the support of the external IT company.

The project leaders explained that the SHAPE-ID consortium did not initially prioritise developing a business model for the toolkit. They felt that exploring potential business models, such as social innovation or consultancy approaches, would have required additional support and resources outside the short-term project's scope. This highlights the challenges many research projects face in securing funding and expertise to explore sustainable business models for their outputs, even when they recognise the potential for broader impact and adoption.

¹⁹ <https://www.shapeidtoolkit.eu/about/>

The SHAPE-ID website remains active, however, very little new content has been added. This lack of activity is because all the editors who work on the toolkit are volunteers, and they don't have the capacity to keep the website updated. One of the editors explained that they periodically check the website's content and links to ensure they are still accurate, as websites require ongoing maintenance. They mentioned that links often break, organisations restructure their websites, and information gets moved around. This editor aims to do this approximately every quarter but admitted that staying on top of it is an ongoing challenge. The lack of funding to support regular maintenance is the most significant obstacle faced by the SHAPE-ID Toolkit and similar projects, making it difficult for them to remain current and useful.

Guidelines

1. Developing a sustainability model to be implemented after completing the funding period.

This guideline emphasises the crucial need to proactively plan for digital projects' long-term financial and operational sustainability. Creators should consider diverse sustainability models early in the project lifecycle, exploring options such as:

- a. **Community ownership and governance.** Transitioning the project to a community-led initiative with shared responsibility for maintenance and updates. This can foster a sense of ownership and ensure continued relevance to the target audience.
- b. **Freemium or subscription models.** Offering basic access to the toolkit for free while charging for premium features or content. This can generate revenue to support ongoing maintenance and development.
- c. **Institutional partnerships.** Seeking collaborations with research institutions, universities, or libraries to integrate the toolkit into their existing infrastructure and services. This can provide stable hosting, technical support, and access to a broader user base.
- d. **Grant funding.** Actively pursuing grants or donations from foundations and organisations that support open access initiatives and digital scholarship. This can provide crucial financial resources for long-term sustainability.

The Lab will support innovators in the preparation of a coherent sustainability strategy.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

2. Difersifying the sustianability model into intellectual and technical maintenance.

Intellectual sustainability ensures the project remains valuable and relevant from a knowledge perspective, while technical sustainability ensures its accessibility and functionality over time. Those aspects may require different approaches and resources within the project’s sustainability plan.

- a. **Intellectual sustainability** refers to the ongoing curation, updating, and enrichment of the project's content and knowledge base. It ensures the project remains relevant, accurate, and engaging for its target audience. Intellectual sustainability entails knowledge curation, content updates and revisions and editorial oversight.
- b. **Technical sustainability** focuses on the infrastructure and technical aspects that ensure the project remains accessible, functional, and secure. Key elements of technical sustainability include hosting services, software updates and maintenance, data backup and recovery, day-to-day support and troubleshooting.

3. Ensuring sufficient resources to support a dedicated staff responsible for maintaining the tool, encompassing infrastructure and content.

This guideline underscores the importance of dedicated personnel for the long-term success of digital projects. Securing funding or resources to support a dedicated individual or team is crucial for enacting the sustainability model and maintaining the output.

4. Develop a contingency plan for situations where existing sustainability models prove insufficient

This guideline acknowledges that despite best efforts, some projects may face unforeseen challenges or resource limitations that hinder their long-term sustainability. In such cases, a contingency plan ensures the preservation and continued accessibility of valuable project resources. This involves identifying suitable repositories that align with the project's disciplinary focus and data types. Consider factors such as long-term preservation policies, metadata standards, access policies, and reputation within the community. The next step is to prepare resources for deposit according to the repository's submission guidelines. This may involve data cleaning, format conversion, use of persistent identifiers and the creation of comprehensive documentation. The Lab will be able to assist with preparing the contingency plan if needed.

A good practice would be to enact a contingency plan parallel to other sustainability models to diversify the preservation measures. It should be noted that the SHAPE-ID toolkit follows this logic by depositing its outputs on Zenodo while actively seeking to maintain the standalone toolkit.

2.2.2. Recommender System for OAPEN

The OAPEN OA Book Recommender tool aims to help users find relevant open access books in the OAPEN Library. It is an algorithm based on text mining that can be implemented on one's database. Currently, it is a prototype of a scalable service for library platforms collecting metadata and full-text content.

Value proposition

While recommender systems of commercial web platforms collect personal data to create product recommendations, the OAPEN OA Book recommender only uses the content of open access books. Text mining techniques are employed to determine the most relevant subjects per book. The system can identify the book's core topics and themes by filtering out common words and focusing on unique combinations of three consecutive words ("trigrams") frequently used in a book. This process effectively distills the essence of the text, revealing its specific subject matter. By comparing these subject descriptions, the system can find comparable titles. This approach enables users to discover relevant books without compromising their privacy. The underlying principle, as explained by the project creator, relies on identifying shared textual patterns, or "trigrams," within books. The more trigrams two books have in common, the stronger their connection. This simple yet effective method, conceived and tested by the developer, proved surprisingly successful in generating meaningful recommendations.

The algorithm is simple and can be applied in other domains. This could present a path towards the service's sustainability as it could be implemented for libraries or other platforms based on texts and paid for as a widget.

Target audiences

The tool was developed primarily for users of the OAPEN Library. However, in its current form, it is being developed into a service offered to libraries and service providers for libraries.

Implementation

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

The OAPEN Recommender System was developed by Ronald Snijder, Eric Hellman, and Stevens University of Technology students. Initially, it was Snijder's side job, but others have since taken it over. The creator remains in the capacity of a tester and “quality assurance” manager. The code is available on Github, but as a service, it is only in a prototype phase. It is tested on the OAPEN resources but has not yet been used on any other. The tool has not yet been tested in production, as it was only tested on the OAPEN and students’ test environments. It is a challenge to push it further.

Challenges

The biggest challenge for the creators of the recommender is the lack of time for effective project management. Investment is required to push the solution to the level of a beta service. If there was a stable team, it could be moved from a proof of concept phase to a prototype and then to a viable product. The project's creator outlined his intentions for the future development of the prototype. His immediate goal was to refine the prototype into a functional and deployable "widget" within the current year (2024): “It's sort of a fun project, so I don't mind doing it at night. “ Looking ahead, he anticipated the need to secure external resources, including technical expertise and potentially funding, to ensure the project's continued progress and broader dissemination.

Guidelines

- 1. Provide support, such as an external consultant, of the concept/idea from the early stages of a project.**

This guideline emphasises the importance of early-stage support for innovative projects. Engaging an external consultant can provide valuable benefits, including objective assessment and strategic guidance to identify potential strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement in the project's concept and proposed methodology. Consultants can also support project planning and market analysis. Moreover, they often operate in extensive networks and can facilitate connections with potential collaborators, funders, or technology partners. Such consultancy will be one of the services potentially offered by the Lab.

- 2. Assist with finding an investor or a funder who would support service development.**

This guideline highlights the crucial role of funding in enabling the successful development and scaling of innovative projects. The OPERAS Innovation Lab can assist in such efforts by leveraging its network and knowledge of funding opportunities to connect projects with suitable investors, grant programs, or organisations. Similarly, the assistance may include the support in developing compelling funding proposals and identifying potential partners who can contribute resources or expertise. The Lab's support may entail showcasing successful projects to potential stakeholders through its media channels.

3. Support the transition from proof of concept to prototype and ultimately to a viable product.

This guideline focuses on guiding projects through the different stages of development, ensuring a smooth transition from an initial concept to a ready product. The OPERAS Innovation Lab can provide support by providing access to technical experts who can assist with prototyping, testing, and refining the project's technology. This process should be supported by active liaison with potential users and gathering feedback on the prototype. Ultimately, the support should entail guidance and resources to help projects develop sustainable business models that ensure long-term viability.

2.2.3. Transformations: A DARIAH Journal

Transformations: A DARIAH Journal²⁰ enables researchers to publish diverse Digital Humanities outputs (publications linked with underlying research data) for which they often do not get enough academic credit. Before submitting to the journal, authors need to deposit a preprint in an open repository. Transformations welcome ephemeral and experimental scholarly outputs, such as descriptions and analyses of data collections and workflows, annotation practices, software tools, training materials, and traditional academic papers.

Transformations Journal is part of DARIAH Core services and was planned in DARIAH Strategic Plan²¹ (2016-2026). It is hosted on the Episciences platform, and the contributions are previously deposited in institutional repositories (Zenodo, HAL, and other open repositories compliant with OAI/PMH in the future). Episciences has its own publishing system based on the Diamond OA model, which allows it to manage both the editorial workflow and the publication of articles. It enables an open peer review

²⁰ <https://transformations.episciences.org/>

²¹ <https://www.dariah.eu/about/documents-list/>

process – a more innovative way of reviewing (both names of authors and reviewers are known) that DARIAH encourages and advocates for within its communities of researchers.

A key benefit of this project is the enhancement of national repositories within the DARIAH network and the broader AHSS community. This improvement stems from the overlay journal's commitment to utilising open repositories, such as Zenodo and HAL, to preserve and disseminate its content. The project encourages using a wide range of open repositories, provided they adhere to the OAI-PMH protocol for metadata harvesting and interoperability. This approach promotes broader access to scholarly outputs while strengthening the infrastructure for digital scholarship within the AHSS domain.

Value proposition

The journal's goal is to promote better all of the outputs that traditionally remain outside the scope of peer review, including different types of methodological and research activities and more complex research outputs.

This initiative pioneers a novel peer review process to elevate the recognition and value of reviewing activities within research assessment frameworks. By implementing and testing this innovative approach, the project seeks to establish a transparent, fair, and ethically sound publishing model, ultimately contributing to a more robust and equitable system for evaluating scholarly contributions.

"Transformations" seamlessly integrates with the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) environment thanks to Episciences' capacity to communicate with national repositories via the OAI-PMH protocol. It automatically positions the journal within the EOSC ecosystem, enhancing its visibility and discoverability within the European research landscape.

Target audiences

The journal's audience includes research communities working with arts and humanities disciplines and, more broadly, the GLAM sector, partner organisations, or different policy-making bodies, from early career researchers to established researchers.

Implementation

The journal was launched in Spring 2024 after signing the agreement with Episciences. The journal is governed by two bodies: an editorial board and a scientific board. The editorial board has four members: a Chief editor, two managing editors and the DARIAH Communication Officer. The editorial board is responsible for the editorial workflow and managing the article submissions. The scientific board comprises external researchers and experts from the DARIAH network and beyond. The scientific board is responsible for the quality of the journal's scientific content and the submission assessment. It appoints external experts or scientific board members to review the submitted works.

Authors follow a workflow that involves depositing their preprints in a repository and submitting their articles to the journal. The submission undergoes reviews and editing before being accepted. The accepted version must also be published in a repository before publication in the journal.

Challenges

The biggest challenge for an experimental journal at its beginning is reaching potential authors. The editorial team aims to follow DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) guidelines and register on the platform as soon as possible.

The sustainability model relies on a traditional workflow based on voluntary contributions from the editors. This might become a problem in the future, but the creators do not consider it a challenge for now²².

Lastly, the leaders see a challenge in compliance with the assessment criteria of innovative outputs and innovative approaches in the texts: “The challenges I see in this project is really to assess innovative form and outputs better and to help researchers to value all of the resources and to pay special attention to the availability of the resources, software data sets linked to the publication as kind of compulsory requirement when submitting new content.”

²² For more insights on sustainability issues of publishers see DIAMAS report: DIAMAS. ‘The Financial Sustainability of Institutional Publishers and Service Providers in Europe’. Zenodo.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Guidelines

1. Enhance visibility and promote active dissemination within relevant research communities.

A new journal needs visibility. Otherwise, it will not become an impactful scholarly communication tool. “Transformations” needs to be disseminated among DARIAH-related research communities, and the communication needs to be convincing and straightforward so that researchers see value in putting effort into such a publication process. This could be achieved through targeted communication campaigns to reach specific research communities within DARIAH and the broader AHSS landscape, highlighting the journal's unique focus on non-traditional research outputs. Webinars, workshops, and conference presentations could promote the journal among potential authors and reviewers while forging a sense of community around it. The Lab will offer assistance in sketching communication strategy and, via the Observatory website, support networking and dissemination of innovative projects.

2. Facilitate networking and knowledge exchange with other venues facing similar challenges.

This guideline highlights the importance of collaboration and knowledge sharing among initiatives exploring innovative scholarly communication approaches. Cooperation with related journals and platforms sharing similar goals and target audiences will enable journals to cross-promote initiatives and expand reach (see the following case study).

3. Advocate for broader recognition and support for innovative outputs and research practices

More generally, such projects need advocacy for innovative outputs and research, not only because they are innovative but also because they support innovation. There is a need for systemic change in research evaluation to ensure that innovative outputs and research practices are adequately recognised and valued. The OPERAS Innovation Lab, along with the innovators themselves, can contribute by raising awareness among stakeholders (research institutions, funders, and policymakers) to showcase and highlight the importance of innovative research and advocate for its inclusion in evaluation criteria. Additionally, based on their practical experience, innovators should develop guidelines that provide actionable recommendations for evaluating innovative outputs and integrating them into research assessment processes. Such actions will be closely linked to the general visibility enhancement effort outlined above.

4. Consider sustainability challenges as early as possible.

Though they may not be considered a challenge now, it is helpful to perform a self-check to assess the financial sustainability of your institutional publishing with a DIAMAS Diamond OA Sustainability Check tool²³.

2.2.4. Journal of Digital History

The Journal of Digital History (JDH)²⁴ is a peer-reviewed OA journal. Papers must contain three layers defined by the editorial board. Based on code notebooks, articles include:

1. A narration layer exploring the possibilities of multimedia storytelling.
2. A hermeneutic layer highlighting the methodological implications of using digital tools, data and code.
3. A data layer provides access to data and makes it reusable (when possible).

Each layer is evaluated using a single anonymised peer-review procedure. The C²DH runs JDH) – a unit based at the University of Luxembourg. It is supported by the University of Luxembourg and the De Gruyter publishing group. The issues are available both in the interactive format and in PDF (however, the third layer is usually omitted in the latter).

Value proposition

The novelty of JDH lies in the publishing methodology. The journal editor explained that the project was initially motivated by the lack of suitable venues for publishing research that integrated digital methods with historical inquiry. Existing options tended to fall into two categories: digital humanities/history journals, which primarily focused on methodological discussions, and traditional history journals, which emphasised research findings. This division created a problematic separation, limiting the potential for cross-disciplinary dialogue and hindering the integration of digital approaches within mainstream historical scholarship.

²³ Consortium of the DIAMAS project. 'Diamond OA Sustainability Check Statements'. Zenodo.

²⁴ <https://journalofdigitalhistory.org/en>

The journal aimed to create a space for historians and digital historians to meet and discuss their methods. It serves as a forum for critical debate and discussion in the field of digital history by offering an innovative publication platform and promoting a new form of data-driven scholarship and transmedia storytelling in the historical sciences.

Target audiences

The Journal of Digital History is predominantly aimed at both historians and digital historians who wish to avoid separating their methods from their results.

Implementation

JDH was launched in Autumn 2021. The team comprises one developer, one designer (both hired specifically for the journal), and editors from C2DH. The team uses the C2DH infrastructure. Production of one JDH issue is very time-consuming. The initial work on the journal started in 2019, with the team expanding in 2020, but because of the long technical review process, the first issue was available in autumn 2021.

Challenges

The challenge lies in finding authors with content to publish in the Journal. Also, finding peer reviewers is even more of a challenge. Two types of reviewers are required: ones who are able to review the technical layer and others who can work on the other two layers. The reviews used to be double anonymised, but due to the problems in collaboration, the JDH editors decided to switch to a single-blind review.

For the reasons mentioned above, the team is constantly reorganising and seeking new management methods and workflows.

Guidelines

The Journal of Digital History and Transformations share numerous similarities. Both push boundaries in scholarly communication within the AHSS domain and face similar challenges with reviewing and recognition. Thus, while reiterating some points, these guidelines focus on JDH's unique needs.

1. **Facilitate networking and knowledge exchange with other venues facing similar challenges.**

Establish a platform or forum specifically for editors of journals that publish digital or innovative scholarship. This would enable them to share experiences, discuss challenges (e.g., finding reviewers, managing complex workflows), and

exchange best practices. This could entail organising workshops and mutual-learning events where editors can discuss common challenges and explore collaborative solutions.

2. Provide guidance and support in developing robust and sustainable editorial workflows.

Given the technical complexity of the submission and reviewing process, which requires additional competence from scholars, there is a need for training and mentorship opportunities for editors and reviewers on topics such as evaluating digital scholarship, working with open-source tools, and managing complex workflows. Additionally, tailored guidance could be prepared and offered on managing peer review for multi-layered digital publications. Additionally, some system of incentives and rewards for editorial work could be established.

2.3. Validation

The validation of the case studies was conducted in the form of a workshop with experts during the OPERAS 2024 conference. Through focused group discussions, participants contributed to the debate on three main challenges that were the outcome of the desk research and interview analysis:

1. **Sustainability:** How can innovative projects transcend the constraints of funding cycles and institutional inertia?
2. **Networking and Visibility:** How can we ensure that innovative work reaches its intended audience and fosters meaningful collaboration?
3. **Research Assessment:** How can we create a framework that recognises the unique contributions of innovative SSH outputs?

2.3.1. Sustainability through collaboration

The sustainability challenge is a perennial one for innovators in the SSH. The workshop participants emphasised the importance of early planning, community engagement, and strategic partnerships. They stressed the need to develop sustainable business models, create toolkits for reproducibility, and leverage existing projects to maximise resources. Ultimately, the key role was played by the power of collaboration. By working together, we can build a more sustainable future for innovative SSH projects.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

2.3.2. Strategies for visibility and networking

Within the contemporary information landscape, characterised by an abundance of information, ensuring the visibility of innovative projects is crucial. Workshop participants advocated for developing communication strategies that leverage social media, face-to-face interactions, and the expertise of institutional communication departments. The emphasis was on identifying and cultivating relationships with key stakeholders who can amplify the reach and impact of innovative work. Crafting a targeted communication strategy and outlining clear objectives, channels, and timelines to reach niche SSH audiences effectively were deemed essential. The workshop underscored the value of face-to-face interactions in establishing alliances, leveraging onsite events to connect with potential collaborators and end-users, and harnessing the power of institutional communication channels to amplify the project's message.

2.3.3. Reimagining Research Assessment

The research assessment group grappled with the fundamental questions of what to evaluate (innovators, institutions, or outputs) and how to do it reasonably. The lack of clear definitions for innovative outputs presented a significant hurdle, highlighting the need for a comprehensive framework to recognise and reward these contributions. To address this issue, workshop participants proposed ten assessment criteria combining qualitative and quantitative measures, ranging from novelty and utility to user engagement and sustainability. They also emphasised the importance of peer review principles, reviewer training, and technological solutions like digital integrity certificates. To revolutionise research assessment, however, participants recognised the need for political action, advocating for the inclusion of well-defined innovative outputs in international agreements and declarations that could reshape the landscape of scholarly evaluation.²⁵

2.3.4. Conclusion

The six-month study, which sought to gather insights directly from innovators while illuminating common challenges, revealed diverse support needs across projects. This realisation has been pivotal for the Innovation Lab, as it necessitates tailoring our services to our target audience's specific requirements and resources. This exploration of sustainability, visibility, and research assessment challenges informs the Lab's activities as it forges a more supportive and inclusive ecosystem for SSH innovation.

²⁵ <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/07/15/navigating-sustainability-visibility-and-research-assessment/>

3. Evaluation and Research Assessment

The OPERAS Innovation Lab works towards a landscape where groundbreaking digital tools and innovative research outputs are not just acknowledged but truly valued. This chapter delves into how we can make this a reality by building upon the case studies of innovative outputs in AHSS and proposing a comprehensive evaluation framework for such projects.

Grounded in the principles of the DORA declaration²⁶ and the CoARA agreement²⁷, this framework advocates for a broader recognition of research outputs and the crucial role of research infrastructures in supporting innovation. Informed by the stakeholders' insights from the validation workshop "How to Support Innovation in Social Sciences and Humanities?"²⁸, ten criteria for assessing innovative projects were formulated, encompassing aspects such as novelty, utility, and sustainability. These criteria are applied to four case studies, demonstrating their practical application. Finally, this chapter explores the international declarations and agreements in the context of promoting wider recognition of innovative outputs within the research assessment landscape.

3.1. Context and methodology

DORA²⁹ and CoARA³⁰ advocate for a comprehensive approach to research assessment. They recommend evaluating all research outputs alongside traditional publications, including datasets and software. Both documents highlight the importance of considering a diverse range of impact measures, including qualitative indicators such as influence on policy and practice, to gain a holistic understanding of research contributions. This approach moves beyond a narrow focus on publication metrics, recognising scholarly activities' multifaceted value and impact. CoARA particularly emphasises the importance of recognising diverse research outputs and valuing a broad range of impacts, promoting a more inclusive and comprehensive approach to research assessment.

²⁶ San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment: <https://sfдора.org/>

²⁷ Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>

²⁸ See the workshop details:

<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/conference-workshops-details/#workshop-2>

²⁹ <https://sfдора.org/read/>, recommendation number 3.

³⁰ <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>, commitment number 6.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

In this evaluation framework, research infrastructures “have a great deal of experience creating and maintaining public services for producing, curating and harvesting both traditional and non-traditional academic outputs”³¹ and can contribute efficiently to reforming the Research assessment framework. Research Infrastructures aim to support researchers and institutions in receiving better academic credit for the diversity of digital tools and research outputs they develop, produce, and share around research infrastructures.

This chapter discusses concrete recommendations and criteria for recognising and rewarding innovative research outputs within research assessment frameworks. Acknowledging the need for systemic change at the international level, we advocate for incorporating these recommendations into political action and policy-making. This includes actively promoting the inclusion of diverse, innovative outputs in international declarations and agreements on Open Access and Research Assessment, thereby driving a shift towards a more inclusive and comprehensive evaluation of scholarly contributions.

These guidelines are mainly grounded in the collective knowledge and participants' feedback of the validation workshop in Zadar³². Three overarching themes were identified during the workshop, and two (sustainability and networking) were discussed in greater detail in the previous chapter. This section zooms in on the third key challenge, namely the research assessment: How can we create a framework that recognises the unique contributions of innovative AHSS projects and outputs?

The evaluation guidelines apply to the same case studies³³ and can be followed by researchers willing to engage with similar formats or projects.

³¹ Toma Tasovac, Laurent Romary, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Rahel C. Ackermann, Daniel Alves, et al.. The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper. 2023. ([hal-04136772](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-04136772))

³² First, workshop participants proposed eight assessment criteria combining qualitative and quantitative measures, ranging from novelty and utility to user engagement and sustainability. But we expand them to ten criteria for the purpose of the guidelines.

³³ See more: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/innovative-outputs/innovation-lab-case-study/>

3.2. Cross-cutting questions on evaluation changes in AHSS

3.2.1 Research Infrastructures and Innovation

Why is it essential to support innovation? Innovators may rely on solid research infrastructure that provides financial and human resources and technical tools and services to develop and sustain their new projects in the long term. Still, many innovators are obliged to conduct their research projects abroad because of the lack of support in their own research unit or institution and country.³⁴

The forthcoming DARIAH position paper on innovation emphasises the enduring role of the Arts and Humanities in driving societal change. In today's digital age, these disciplines have unprecedented opportunities to shape societal transformation by harnessing the creative potential of researchers and research communities. This potential is closely linked to the evolving roles of galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM sector), advancements in digital education, and pioneering research in areas such as Cultural (Big) Data, the Collections as Data initiative, and the Internet of (Cultural) Things. As Digital Arts and Humanities evolve, they are poised to significantly contribute to cultural and creative value chains beyond purely economic measures. Moreover, they have the potential to inform policy-making at the European level, particularly given the increasing focus on the cultural and creative sector.³⁵

During the validation workshop, we raised several dimensions and issues of innovation with regard to the evaluation guidelines:

- What is the unit of evaluation? Should we evaluate innovators, individual researchers, projects, research units or only the outputs?
- How long does the innovative nature of a project last?
- What is the nature of innovative outputs, and what should be the scope and the type of innovation?

³⁴ Par Laure Belot. 2023. 'Bertin Nahum, serial innovateur de robots chirurgicaux'. Le Monde, 14 October 2023.

https://www.lemonde.fr/sciences/article/2023/10/14/bertin-nahum-serial-innovateur-de-robots-chirurgicaux_6194438_1650684.html.

³⁵ DARIAH Innovation position paper (draft version).

- Should the copyright issues hindering the reusability be part of the evaluation process?

The recent ALLEA report ‘Recognising Digital Scholarly Outputs in the Humanities’³⁶ considers a broad range of digital scholarly outputs, such as digital scholarly editions, extended publications, databases and datasets, visual representations (infographics and maps), code, blogs, and podcasts. In the framework proposed in this chapter, we decided to focus on projects or tools and, more specifically, our case studies.

3.2.2 Quality assessment of innovative research in AHSS

The work of OPERAS Innovation Lab within the OPERAS-P project explored the intricacies of peer review in SSH, seeking to understand its current landscape and potential for innovation.³⁷ The research concluded that traditional peer review is deeply intertwined with academic power structures, often prioritising established publication venues and conventional outputs over innovation and diversity. This creates a self-perpetuating cycle that hinders recognising and rewarding novel approaches and diverse content types, such as digital art, data, and software. A key challenge identified was the scarcity of reviewers, which impacts the efficiency and openness of peer review processes, further reinforcing existing hierarchies.

Despite the push for open and reproducible peer review within the Open Science paradigm, the study found that SSH communities prioritise broadening the scope of peer review to encompass a broader range of outputs. There was notable resistance to fully open peer review, with a preference for publishing review texts anonymously alongside publications, highlighting a desire for transparency while preserving reviewer anonymity. The research also underscored the significance of informal peer review mechanisms that organically arise within SSH communities, driven by a passion for scholarly dialogue and knowledge advancement. Recognising these informal practices and their motivations is crucial for developing more effective and inclusive evaluation systems that better align with the evolving realities of SSH research.

Building on these findings, the current study delves deeper into evaluating innovative projects and outputs. The traditional research assessment metrics, focused on articles

³⁶ Böbe Barsi. 2023. ‘Recognising Digital Scholarly Outputs in the Humanities (ALLEA Report)’. Billet. *DARIAH Open* (blog). <https://doi.org/10.58079/veoc> ; Wnuk, Magdalena, Maciej Maryl. 2024. ‘How to Evaluate Innovation in the Humanities?’ *OPERAS Innovation Lab Observatory* (blog). <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/01/24/how-to-evaluate-innovation-in-the-humanities/>.

³⁷ Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Marta Błaszczynska, Anna Buchner, and Maciej Maryl. 2021. ‘OPERAS-P Deliverable D6.6: Report on Quality Assessment of Innovative Research in SSH’. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922538>.

and monographs, often fail to capture the value of research diversity. One of the reasons is the lack of established quality-assurance mechanisms with regard to non-traditional scholarly work. That calls for creating the proper assessment criteria for innovative formats and contributions that fall outside conventional publishing models to avoid their marginalisation. The growing interest in more open and transparent peer review practices, including open review reports, participation, and identities, resonates with the aim of this current study, which is to develop a more inclusive and equitable evaluation framework for innovative projects and outputs in the AHSS. By examining the limitations of existing assessment systems and exploring alternative approaches, this research seeks to recognise better and reward the diverse contributions of AHSS scholars.

3.3. Building criteria for the evaluation of innovation

Against the backdrop of the findings, which underscore the limitations of traditional research assessment and the need for more inclusive and nuanced approaches, this study proposes a set of criteria specifically designed to address the question raised at the Zadar Workshop (see section 2.3. Validation).

3.3.1. Ten dimensions for evaluating innovative project

Establishing a clear and understandable framework is essential to effectively assess innovative projects and their outputs in AHSS. This necessitates identifying key criteria and providing detailed definitions for each, ensuring clarity and consistency in their application. The following section outlines ten such criteria, each accompanied by a comprehensive explanation, to guide the assessment of innovative projects and contribute to a more robust and inclusive research evaluation system. These measures are aligned with CoARA's vision that research assessment should rely primarily on qualitative assessment for which peer review is central. Proposing new qualitative criteria for assessing the quality and impact of innovative projects and their outputs is explored here alongside peer review.

1. Novelty

Originality of the idea. Does the project bring new research process methods, practices, and innovative content? Novelty is not necessarily disruptive, but it changes traditional forms and ways of doing research. The project novelty may also lie in repurposing the existing technology and standards for the novel content.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

2. Utility

Addressing a need. Is the innovation responding to a need identified in research practices or the discipline? Will the innovative project help specific academic communities?

3. User engagement

Usability of the application. Functionalities of the project (service or tool) that enable users to collaborate or contribute. This can include usage metrics or other indicators of community uptake.³⁸

4. User responsiveness

Adaptability of the application. Capacity to provide a robust, accessible, and adaptable service or tool to all devices according to different uses.

5. Impact and collaboration

Capacity to develop science communication and interaction with society, entrepreneurship, knowledge valorisation, and industry-academia cooperation. The service should provide the framework for interdisciplinary exchange and disciplinary expertise.

6. Bridging potential

Capacity of the project or tool to propose multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinary as well as inter-sectoral approaches. Transgress boundaries between disciplinary knowledge.

7. Support and training for users

Capacity to document and describe the new technology and make it readily available for the tool's users. Are training materials, support/helpdesk available?

8. Sustainability

Capacity to manage the support and maintenance of the innovation (in time) thanks to funding, institutional support (robust infrastructure), human resources, and Open Science policy or rules.

³⁸ Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet. 2021. 'Rethinking Text, Techné and Tenure: Evaluation and Peer Review Challenges around Virtual Research Environments in the Arts and Humanities – Classics@ Journal'. *Classics@ Journal* 18 (1). <https://classics-at.chs.harvard.edu/classics18-toth-czifra/>.

9. Peer review/evaluation process or workflow

Methods of peer review (Open Peer Review is preferred to single/double anonymised) used for the project. The capacity to provide an open and transparent evaluation framework enables better recognition for reviewers, more equity for authors, and a transparent framework for discussing ongoing research.

10. Reusability / reproducibility

Openness of research and results that are verifiable and reproducible (data reuse, protocols, workflows under open licences). Is the project's data harvestable by other services and available to other users and projects?

3.3.2 Criteria compliance for the case studies

Having established a clear framework for evaluating innovation, this section applies the ten criteria to the four case studies presented earlier. This analysis examines the presence and operability of each criterion within each case, providing insights into their strengths and areas for potential development.

Criterion	Compliance per case study
Novelty	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = provides pathways to IDR (interdisciplinary research) and TDR (transdisciplinary research).
	OAPEN = algorithm based on text mining that can be implemented on one's database. It works across languages.
	Transformations = uses Episciences Diamond publishing platform, where contributions are previously deposited in repositories. It's a new publishing model in the discipline of Arts and Humanities.
	JDH = sets new standards in publishing history scholarship based on a novel multi-layered approach. Papers must contain the three layers that are characteristic of the JDH.
Utility	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = helps navigate knowledge available in various sources.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

	<p>OAPEN = helps users find relevant open-access books in the OAPEN Library (prototype).</p>
	<p>Transformations = improves the quality of DARIAH national repositories wishing to connect to Episciences, a non-commercial platform for documenting various methodological and research activities in the arts and humanities, including data gathering and processing, annotation and modelling, analysis, and interpretation.</p>
	<p>JDH = creates a space where historians and digital historians meet and discuss their methods.</p>
<p>User engagement</p>	<p>SHAPE-ID Toolkit = addresses support for different roles (individual, research organisation, research funder, societal partner) in improving research skills, dissemination, evaluation, and collaboration.</p>
	<p>OAPEN = provides recommendations to readers (without tracking personal data).</p>
	<p>Transformations = editors contributing to evaluating the contents using an open peer review process; authors opening their research outputs using repositories beforehand and submitting them to the Episciences platform.</p>
	<p>JDH = provides Github script for a notebook check.</p>
<p>User responsiveness</p>	<p>SHAPE-ID Toolkit offers guided pathways and tailored resources for each user's role (from four different groups).</p>
	<p>OAPEN = tool is tested on the OAPEN resources and might be scaled to other databases</p>
	<p>Transformations = Episciences offers daily support in the use of the software.</p>
	<p>JDH = Jupyter Notebooks are at the heart of the edition and exploration of articles.</p>

Impact and collaboration	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = engages and communicates with collaborators from other disciplines and sectors through face-to-face interactions and the expertise of institutional communication departments.
	OAPEN = service offered to libraries and service providers for libraries.
	Transformations = contributes to developing the Diamond publishing model internationally; promotes and recognises complex research outputs, which improves visibility in the EOSC environment.
	JDH = as an international peer-reviewed open-access journal, JDH sets new standards in history publishing based on a novel multi-layered approach.
Bridging potential	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = fosters inter-and transdisciplinarity Research in AHSS (IDR/TDR).
	OAPEN = trigrams are a unique method of discovery that bridges resources from various disciplines
	Transformations = research communities working with arts and humanities disciplines and, more broadly, the GLAM sector are the targeted audiences.
	JDH = The journal serves as a forum for critical debate and discussion in the field of digital history by offering an innovative publication platform and promoting a new form of data-driven scholarship and of transmedia storytelling in the historical sciences.
Support and training for users	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = "guided pathways" for researchers, science managers, and resources.
	OAPEN = DOAB-Check website helps to improve DOAB metadata.
	Transformations = Episciences provides tools for authors to submit a contribution and for Editorial teams to use the publishing platform.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

	JDH = provides guidelines for authors.
Sustainability/ business model	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = no time to develop a business model.
	OAPEN = could be implemented for libraries or other platforms based on texts and paid for as a widget.
	Transformations = Diamond open access allows immediate free access—without identification or DRM—to publications through their deposit in an open archive. Episciences is supported by CCSD, jointly ensured by its supervising bodies (CNRS, Inria, INRAE) and the Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESR).
	JDH = Full OA journal. All authors retain copyright unless – due to their local circumstances – their work is not copyrighted. It is run by the C2DH - a unit at the University of Luxembourg and supported by the University and the De Gruyter publishing group.
Peer review / evaluation process or workflow	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = provides evaluation criteria tools for IDR/TDR projects.
	OAPEN = does not apply
	Transformations = The Evaluation system relies on Open Identities, but review reports will not be published.
	JDH = is a single anonymized peer-reviewed journal. Papers must contain the three layers that are characteristic of the JDH. Each layer is evaluated using an anonymized peer-review procedure.
Reusability / Reproducibility	SHAPE-ID Toolkit = some resources are under Creative Commons licensing.
	OAPEN = the code is available on GitHub.
	Transformations = all journal contents are Creative Commons, Attribution CC-BY 4.0.

JDH = articles and datasets are published under the Creative Commons licence, Attribution CC-BY-NC-ND (authors can opt for CC-BY), e.g. Episciences technical support and bug reporting service [GitHub](#).

3.4. Sustaining innovation: assessing and contextualising innovative outputs

To sustain innovation in the long term, it's crucial to work with specific innovation teams on the organisational and evaluation sides and combine qualitative and quantitative criteria to elaborate concrete pointers to analyse the 'innovation' compliance of tools or projects.

3.4.1 Building and organising a new peer-review framework

To properly assess the innovation dimension in a qualitative evaluation process, reviewers should first rely on Open Science requirements to ensure the fairness and openness of the project.

The FAIR principles³⁹ describe how research outputs should be organised to be more easily accessed, understood, exchanged and reused. Meanwhile, the CARE principles describe how data should be treated to ensure that Indigenous governance over the data and its use are respected.⁴⁰

Persistent Unique Identifiers (PIDs) improve the accessibility and openness of digital research outputs and sustainable referencing. As technologies are constantly changing, assigning PIDs to your project will enable reliable, robust and long-term access to the different dimensions of the innovative output. PIDs (Handle, DOI, ARK) should be assigned to varying levels of granularity of the project: the actors (authors, institution/structure, funder, editor), the content (code/software, articles, corpus,

³⁹ Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, I. Jsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3 (March):160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

⁴⁰ Gouzi, Françoise, Laure Barbot, Matej Durco, Sally Chambers, and Toma Tasovac. 2024. 'DARIAH Data Policy'. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/10409010>.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

monographs, datasets), and the documentation (metadata).⁴¹ Once the reviewers have checked these prerequisites have been met, it is also important to provide them with robust and transparent assessment grids of criteria so they can make a tailored review according to the different functionalities and facets of the innovation.

Reviewers must have qualifications and specific skills (e.g. relevant knowledge of the subject and technology) to assess innovative projects and outputs. In terms of peer review principles, different dimensions and criteria are expected and required in the parameters and settings of the creative outputs, such as transparency, reuse, actionability, open identities, and responsibility of authors and reviewers.⁴² The ongoing EC-funded ATRIUM project⁴³ is creating assessment grids of criteria for various research outputs (workflows, data papers, training materials), intending to obtain better recognition for those and provide a more transparent and solid framework for the reviewers. By building community consensus around a peer review framework, ATRIUM aims to incentivise various research outputs necessary for building and maintaining innovative research infrastructures.

3.4.2 Recognition in international declarations

Promoting visibility and reuse within the scholarly communication ecosystem is essential to fostering more comprehensive recognition and adoption of innovative outputs. Platforms like OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, and the SSH Open Marketplace offer valuable channels for disseminating and showcasing these outputs, facilitating their discovery and uptake by researchers and other stakeholders. This approach aligns with Open Science principles, which advocate for open sharing to maximise research impact and encourage collaboration.

However, more than wider dissemination is required. To truly integrate innovative outputs into the research assessment landscape, a concerted effort is needed from various stakeholders. This includes research teams, research performing organisations, and international institutions, who must collaborate to advocate for the inclusion of diverse outputs in national research assessment frameworks. Furthermore, achieving this goal requires political action to embed recognition of innovative outputs in international agreements and declarations on research assessment. This will contribute

⁴¹Kálman Tibor, Introduction to Persistent Identifiers. Version 1.0.0. DARIAH-Campus. [Webinar recording]. 2022 <https://campus.dariah.eu/id/4uEjJqTVxczKYmJyc3w9n>

⁴² Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet, Marta Błaszczewska, Anna Buchner, and Maciej Maryl. 2021. 'OPERAS-P Deliverable D6.6: Report on Quality Assessment of Innovative Research in SSH', April.

⁴³ <https://atrium-research.eu/objectives/>

to a more inclusive and comprehensive evaluation system that values the full spectrum of scholarly contributions.

This section examines four such international agreements and declarations, exploring their potential to promote greater recognition of innovative services and outputs, particularly given their existing emphasis on "bibliodiversity"⁴⁴ and the societal impact of research.

Manifesto on Science as Global Public Good

The Global Summit on Diamond Open Access, held in Toluca, Mexico, in October 2023, exemplified collaborative policy action in research assessment. This summit, co-organized by a coalition of international organisations, including Redalyc, UNESCO, and OPERAS, brought together diverse stakeholders to advocate for non-commercial Open Access and the recognition of "Science as a Global Public Good." The resulting Manifesto⁴⁵ emphasises equity, diversity, and inclusivity principles in scholarly communication, urging a shift towards a more equitable and accessible research landscape. This initiative demonstrates a growing momentum towards reforming research assessment to better value diverse outputs and knowledge dissemination models.

The Manifesto champions a vision of scholarly communication that prioritises equity, accessibility, and the recognition of diverse research contributions while criticising the commercialisation of Open Access, mainly through article processing charges (APCs) and transformative agreements. Instead, the Manifesto advocates for Diamond and Green Open Access, where publications are free to read and publish, upholding the values of inclusivity and non-rivalrous consumption of knowledge.

Crucially, the Manifesto calls for research assessment systems to recognise and value non-commercial modes of scholarly communication. It urges funding agencies and institutions to acknowledge the contributions of Diamond Open Access journals and platforms, ensuring that researchers are rewarded for participating in these initiatives.

To be fully recognised within this framework, evaluators and innovators must explicitly acknowledge this public good dimension. This involves providing inclusive and free access platforms, tools, and systems for both creators and consumers of knowledge, as exemplified by initiatives like Transformations or JDH. However, the case studies reveal

⁴⁴ <https://www.coalition-s.org/diamond-open-access/>

⁴⁵ <https://globaldiamantoa.org/manifiesto/#/>

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

the challenges of fostering collaboration across disciplines and sectors during project development and sustained maintenance. Therefore, the principle of collaboration should extend beyond immediate partnerships to encompass integration within broader open research infrastructures. Connecting with such infrastructures in the SSH and AHSS domains provides access to crucial support, including technology, networking opportunities, open science policies, and tailored services, ultimately enhancing the project's security and sustainability.

San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)

The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)⁴⁶ advocates for a Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) framework that provides research assessment policies and tools for institutions (at the international level). It has become a worldwide initiative covering all scholarly disciplines and key stakeholders, including funders, publishers, professional societies, institutions, and researchers.

TARA (Tools to Advance Research Assessment), part of DORA, provides a more practical dimension that could help assess innovative projects' impact and sustainability. “Building Blocks for Impact” is a one-pager that outlines and illustrates various academic achievements and outcomes that could be considered “impactful”. This model visualises “impact” in two dimensions: the scale of the influence of contributions and the influence of new types of audiences.

CoARA agreement

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a European initiative to reform research assessment practices. It provides a platform for stakeholders across the research landscape to collaboratively develop and implement more responsible and inclusive approaches to evaluating research contributions. CoARA's commitment to recognising diverse research outputs and valuing a broad range of impacts aligns with the goals of promoting innovative scholarship within the AHSS.

In this context, fostering closer collaboration between public research infrastructures (RIs) and research assessment organisations is essential, as DARIAH-EU advocates in its position paper on Research Assessment Reform⁴⁷. RIs play a crucial role in supporting researchers who engage in Open Science practices and utilise innovative outputs,

⁴⁶ <https://sfedora.org/resource/rethinking-research-assessment-building-blocks-for-impact/>

⁴⁷ Tasovac, Toma, Laurent Romary, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Rahel C. Ackermann, Daniel Alves, Sally Chambers, Mike Cosgrave, et al. 2023. ‘The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper’. <https://hal.science/hal-04136772>.

advocating for their recognition at both individual and national levels. Simultaneously, innovators and scholars rely on public RIs to provide the necessary infrastructure and support for creating, managing, and disseminating their work, facilitating a smoother research assessment process.

CoARA's sixth commitment⁴⁸, explicitly focusing on reviewing and developing research assessment criteria, tools, and processes, offers a valuable entry point for enhancing the visibility, recognition, and evaluation of innovative outputs. By advocating for the inclusion of disciplinary, multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinary research and diverse contributions to knowledge generation and societal impact, CoARA promotes a more inclusive and comprehensive approach to research assessment that can better accommodate the unique contributions of innovative scholarship.

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information⁴⁹, an initiative advocating for greater transparency and accessibility in research, calls for a fundamental shift towards open research information. This declaration emphasises the need to make openness the default, to utilise supportive services and systems, to ensure the sustainability of open research infrastructures, and to foster collaborative efforts to transition from closed to open information sharing.

The declaration highlights key commitments⁵⁰ to achieve sustainable infrastructures for open research information. Signatories pledge to actively support these infrastructures through community engagement, governance, and fair financial contributions. Furthermore, they expect supported infrastructures to adhere to community governance and sustainability best practices, such as the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure, ensuring responsible and effective management of open research information.

Open interfaces provided by research infrastructures enable innovative projects to develop and grow long-term alongside standardised protocols and persistent identifiers to support high findability and interoperability or the transparency of processing and provenance to support Interoperability and Reusability.

⁴⁸ <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>

⁴⁹ barcelona-declaration.org

⁵⁰ <https://barcelona-declaration.org/commitments/>

3.5. Conclusion

This chapter explores the critical need for a comprehensive framework to evaluate and support innovative projects and research outcomes in AHSS. Building upon international declarations and initiatives, we employed the insights from case studies to propose ten specific criteria for assessing innovative outputs.

While this evaluation framework offers a crucial foundation, it is essential to acknowledge that projects require more than just assessment. To truly thrive, they need ongoing support, guidance, and resources to navigate the complexities of development, implementation, and long-term sustainability. By combining practical support mechanisms with advocating for suitable evaluation frameworks, the OPERAS Innovation Lab aims to foster a research environment where innovation is not only recognised but actively cultivated and rewarded.

4. Evolution and Future of the Lab

Just like the previous Lab's report⁵¹, we wanted this one to end with a look towards the future rather than concluding closing remarks. The OPERAS Innovation Lab is an initiative to support innovation in open scholarly communication within SSH. It seeks to design and implement repeatable and sustainable innovation processes within OPERAS.

4.1. Structure

Figure 1. Lab's structure

The Lab is organised around two main pillars: the Observatory and the Accelerator. Media channels are responsible for efficient communication with the public, and the "Bank of Ideas" serves as the backbone of the operations.

⁵¹ Maryl, M., Błaszczczyńska, M., Avanço, K., Balula, A., Buchner, A., Caliman, L., Clivaz, C., Costa, C., Franczak, M., Gatti, R., Giglia, E., Gingold, A., Jarmelo, S., Padez, M. J., Leão, D., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Mojsak, K., Morka, A., Mosterd, T., ... Wieneke, L. (2021). *Future of Scholarly Communication. Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>

The Observatory focuses on research and analysis on innovation in open scholarly communication. It gathers case studies, creates guidelines, and publishes reports. The Observatory identifies challenges, monitors trends, and promotes best practices.

The Accelerator supports the development and implementation of innovative solutions. It offers consulting services, training, and support to obtain funding. The Accelerator helps transform ideas into concrete projects, including pilot projects.

The Media are the Lab’s communication channels. They are responsible for communicating and collaborating with the community. They share information about the Lab’s activities, promote its initiatives, and facilitate networking.

The Bank of Ideas is the backbone of OPERAS Innovation Lab’s operations. It is an internal database that collects information on problems, solutions, potential partnerships, and funding opportunities. The "**Bank of Ideas**" platform identifies promising projects and connects relevant stakeholders.

Figure 2. Lab’s internal processes

The OPERAS Innovation Lab collaborates with a wide range of stakeholders, including the OPERAS community, OPERAS governing bodies, and external entities such as industry, non-governmental organisations, and academia.

Looking at the long term, the OPERAS Innovation Lab is planned to be integrated into the structure of the OPERAS ERIC as a strategic activity with continuing support. OPERAS-PL, the Polish National Node of OPERAS⁵², will develop the concept of the Lab's physical presence, understood as a networking facility for innovation support, which could be prototyped if resources allow. Plans are also in place to create an internal funding mechanism (Innovation Fund) and secure additional financial resources from private partners, NGOs, and other institutions.

4.2. Future of OPERAS Innovation Lab

The lab's planned development, aligned with the vision presented above, will occur in three main phases. The timing is indicative.

Phase 1 (2024-2025)

1. Identifying challenges and gathering ideas. The Lab will identify internal challenges, collect ideas to address them and leverage existing resources through research and networking activities. This activity will persist into future phases, with the Observatory serving the pivotal role.

2. Launching a Pilot Portfolio. After testing selected ideas in practice, the Lab aims to develop an initial portfolio of pilots. The structure and method of presenting pilots will be devised in OPERAS-PLUS, while resources for implementing pilots will be secured through new projects starting in 2025.

3. Establishing the "Bank of Ideas." An internal database that gathers information about problems, solutions, potential partnerships, and funding opportunities will be a vital element of the Lab.

Phase 2 (2025-2026)

1. Developing an Innovation Management Model. The goal is to create an effective management model for solutions developed within the Lab. This will be developed through the OPERAS-PLUS project and implemented in OPERAS other initiatives and projects as the model for delivering pilot-type activities.

2. Building Partnerships and Implementing Pilot Projects. The Lab will secure resources to build partnerships and implement pilot projects after OPERAS-PLUS completion, with the use of resources available through new projects

⁵² <https://operas.pl/>

3. **Expanding the Observatory.** The Lab will conduct research relevant to the pilot projects and the OPERAS community to publish the results on the observatory website. The research will be aligned with the current strategic needs of OPERAS.

Phase 3 (2026-2027)

1. Integration into the OPERAS ERIC structure. Ultimately, the Lab aims to become integral to ERIC operations, ensuring its stability and long-term funding.

2. Establishing the Innovation Fund. The Lab will create an internal funding mechanism (Innovation Fund) to support the development and implementation of innovative solutions.

3. Securing External Funding. The Lab will seek additional financial support from private partners, NGOs, and other institutions.

4. Prototyping the physical presence. Along with the ERIC establishment, IBL PAN and OPERAS-PL will seek to launch the Lab's physical space to stimulate the work on innovative services.

4.2.3. Operations

The Lab will offer support, consulting, and training services for OPERAS community members. These activities aim to build competencies in innovation and support the implementation of new solutions. The Lab will also research innovations in open scholarly communication. This will include case study analyses, guidelines development, and report publishing. The research component feeds into both observatory and accelerator work. A significant aspect of the Lab's activities will be collaboration with the OPERAS community, achieved through:

1. Media. Publishing information about its activities, sharing research results, and best practices.

2. Meetings and events will serve as a platform for exchanging experiences and building connections.

3. The Mattermost channel is a dedicated communication channel allowing OPERAS community members to follow the lab's activities and participate in discussions.

The Lab, with its gaze fixed firmly on the future, seeks to amplify its observation and acceleration endeavours and entwine its operations with the evolving OPERAS infrastructure. By fostering sustainable models for project support, cultivating strategic

partnerships, and diligently gathering knowledge on leading-edge practices, the Lab will remain a catalyst for innovation. Through these very efforts, it will secure OPERAS's place as a vital force in advancing open scholarly communication within the social sciences and humanities.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Avanço, Karla, Ana Balula, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Anna Buchner, Lorena Caliman, Claire Clivaz, Carlos Costa, et al. 'Future of Scholarly Communication . Forging an Inclusive and Innovative Research Infrastructure for Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences and Humanities'. Zenodo, 29 June 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>.
- Böbe Barsi. 2023. 'Recognising Digital Scholarly Outputs in the Humanities (ALLEA Report)'. Billet. *DARIAH Open* (blog). <https://doi.org/10.58079/veoc>
- Beck, Susanne, Carsten Bergenholtz, Marcel Bogers, Tiare-Maria Brasseur, Marie Louise Conradsen, Diletta Di Marco, Andreas P. Distel, et al. 'The Open Innovation in Science Research Field: A Collaborative Conceptualisation Approach'. *Industry and Innovation* 29, no. 2 (7 February 2022): 136–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2020.1792274>.
- Consortium of the DIAMAS project. 'Diamond OA Sustainability Check Statements'. Zenodo, 24 September 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13833718>.
- DIAMAS. 'The Financial Sustainability of Institutional Publishers and Service Providers in Europe'. Zenodo, 16 April 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11160815>.
- Gouzi, Françoise, Laure Barbot, Matej Durco, Sally Chambers, and Toma Tasovac. 'DARIAH Data Policy'. Zenodo, 4 January 2024. <https://zenodo.org/records/10409010>.
- Gulbrandsen, Magnus, and Siri Aanstad. 'Is Innovation a Useful Concept for Arts and Humanities Research?' *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education* 14 (16 January 2014): 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474022214533890>.
- Kálman Tibor, Introduction to Persistent Identifiers. Version 1.0.0. DARIAH-Campus. [Webinar recording]. 2022 <https://campus.dariah.eu/id/4uEiJqTVxczKYmJyc3w9n>
- Maryl, Maciej, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Agnieszka Szulińska, Anna Buchner, Piotr Wciślik, Iva Melinščak Zlodi, Jadranka Stojanovski, et al. 'OPERAS-P Deliverable D6.5: Report on the Future of Scholarly Writing in SSH', 30 April 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922512>.
- Poole, Alex H. "'A Greatly Unexplored Area": Digital Curation and Innovation in Digital Humanities'. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 68,

no. 7 (2017): 1772–81. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23743>.

Rieger, Oya Y. 'Opening Up Institutional Repositories: Social Construction of Innovation in Scholarly Communication'. *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 11, no. 3 (30 September 2008). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0011.301>.

Schumpeter, Joseph A. *The Theory of Economic Development: An Inquiry into Profits, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle*. Harvard Economic Studies. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1934.

Tasovac, Toma, Laurent Romary, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Rahel C. Ackermann, Daniel Alves, Sally Chambers, Mike Cosgrave, et al. 'The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper', June 2023. <https://hal.science/hal-04136772..>

Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet. 'Rethinking Text, Techné and Tenure: Evaluation and Peer Review Challenges around Virtual Research Environments in the Arts and Humanities – Classics@ Journal'. *Classics@ Journal* 18, no. 1 (2021). <https://classics-at.chs.harvard.edu/classics18-toth-czifra/>.

Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet, Marta Błaszczńska, Anna Buchner, and Maciej Maryl. 'OPERAS-P Deliverable D6.6: Report on Quality Assessment of Innovative Research in SSH', 30 April 2021.

Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, I. Jsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3 (15 March 2016): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Wnuk, Magdalena, Maciej Maryl. 2024. 'How to Evaluate Innovation in the Humanities?' *OPERAS Innovation Lab Observatory* (blog). <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/01/24/how-to-evaluate-innovation-in-the-humanities/>

Yordanova, Zornitsa, Nikolay Stoimenov, Olga Boyanova, and Ivan Ivanchev. 'The Long Way from Science to Innovation – A Research Approach for Creating an Innovation Project Methodology'. In *Business Information Systems*, edited by Witold Abramowicz and Rafael Corchuelo, 371–80. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20485-3_29.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Case study desk research questionnaire

Basic metadata

FULL NAME: (If the project is available in a language different from English, then both names).

PUBLISHER/OWNER

AUTHORS – INSTITUTIONS: Author as a person/team/institution. Is there an option to join the project? Leading institutions (and partners?).

DATE OF CREATION: (year)

LANGUAGES: Both of the interface and of the content.

LICENCE: E.g. CC/copyright/GNU/other...

Abstract

– 1-2 sentences about the project and its key/specific features

(Potential) Users and their needs

– Back to the history, the reason why the project was developed

– Does the project bridge a gap (if so, what is the gap) -- perhaps it bridges a gap but creates a new one (it should be more info from their page/webinars than our interpretation)?

– Who was it created for? Is it educational? What's the social impact? Are there surveys for users? Was user research conducted?

– Is it meant for individual use or for research teams?

– What is the projected role of users?

– Current aims of the case/project

- Can the users (audience) communicate with one another or with the authors of that case

Data and technology

- Content description (what are the sources, how many objects, are they published elsewhere),)
- Data formats, forms (e.g. presentations, lectures, articles...).
- Is the data published in OA?
- What technology is used (data language, formats)
- Description: features and functionalities (search option, site navigation, programming comments).
- Is it linked to other databases, tools?
- Is the tool part of an integrated tool suite?
- Does it allow for collaboration/teamwork?

Availability and Accessibility

- What are the entry requirements to use it? Do you need to set up an account, show your affiliation to use it?
- Is the access free of charge (if not - what are the payment options)?
- Is the tool accessible via an existing platform? Or does the user's organisation need to install and operate it?
- Is the website accessible to visually impaired users and persons with disabilities? (If not, no need to discuss this)
- Is it possible to use the case differently (based on different user needs, adaptation to different operational systems, mobile devices, etc.)? Compatibility with different devices and systems.
- Is it compatible with different browsers: Chrome, Firefox, Edge, Safari, and mobile devices?

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Sustainability

- Business model.
- Is it funded? What's the source of funding?
- What's the sustainability model (including the technical maintenance including hosting)?
- Is the sustainability model linked to the national context (e.g., in the USA or the UK, it is likely to be more commercial and non-commercial in EU countries)?
- What are the security measures, e.g. data encryption? (This may appear in 'Data and Technology').
- Are there persistent identifiers?

Research assessment

- What assures us about the source's credibility?
- Is it peer-reviewed?
- What kind of evaluation process is involved?
- Does it use alt-metrics?
- Is it in conferences and events? Are there links to social media or institutional websites (university, institute, publisher etc.)?
- Is it indexed in databases (Scopus, DOAB, DOAJ, JSTOR, Web of Science, ERIC, etc.)

Impact

- Examples of usage, number of users, stats, etc.
- Social impact? Education?
- Is the work cited (Google Scholar and others)?
- Prestige: is the venue prestigious? Are there any other prestige-generating mechanisms?
- Communication and promotional strategies: do the creators participate?

Summing up – all innovative aspects

– What is innovative? What kind of innovations are used? What do we find the most innovative about the case? Here we can compare this case with other cases (and if it is not comparable, it is also worth noting!) Could you imagine publishing it as a printed book/e-book/pdf? What would be missing?

– Our UX impressions: Would we have used this in our research? Is the tool easy to use? Is it well documented?

- Which stages of the research workflow are supported by this tool: 1. discovery (data collection, creation, 2. structure (organising, managing research assets), 3. annotation (enriching, curating research assets), 4. analysis (processing, analysing, visualising), 5. publishing (dissemination, communication, review)

Bibliography

The list of texts and resources providing information about the project, is useful for responding to questions above.

Annex 2. Case study interview scenario

Before the interview, it is necessary to fill in the data:

Date:

Interviewer:

Name and Surname of the interviewees:

Name of the project/ output:

Introduction to the OPERAS Innovation Lab and the purpose of the interview.

The Innovation Lab is part of OPERAS, Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. It is coordinated by the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN).

The interview is made as a part of the Work Package 4 OPERAS Plus project. The aim of the interview is to collect information on the project selected to the case study conducted within Task 4.2.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Objective: to name the value and goals from the perspective of project's creators and contributors

1. What was your initial goal and motivation that made you start the project?
2. What was the planned scope: users, accessibility, technologies, budget and funding?
 - What problem do you want to solve?
 - Whose needs does the project address?
 - How do you plan on sustaining it?
 - What is the technology behind it?
3. Has the scope changed so far?

Objective: to identify the workflows and processes from the perspective of the project's creators and contributors

1. How was the project and its workflow designed?
2. How many team members are involved in the project?
 - Please describe the roles and responsibilities.
3. What is your current sustainability model?
4. Who is responsible for proposing changes or developments to the project scope?
5. Who is responsible for adding new features?

Objective: to identify challenges and technology needs

1. What were the main challenges and difficulties during the project's design and implementation (for the more advanced products) phases?
2. What software tools do you lack?
3. What would you need to be able to sustain the project?

Objective: to identify a model for dissemination, promotion and communication

1. What tools and metrics do you use to track the users?
2. How do you communicate with your target users and audiences?